

COMPARE AND CONTRAST IN FAIRY TALES

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the ways of using compare and contrast in enhancing logical and critical thinking using fairy tales. It also proposes the activities which can help enhance the logical reasoning and critical thinking of 4th grade primary school children with the help of several Uzbek fairy tales.*

Keywords: *fairy tales, thinking, logical reasoning, critical thinking, Uzbek fairy tales.*

There are so many ways to teach primary school students how to compare and contrast similar texts, such as compare and contrast fairy tales.

Here are the tips which can help to conduct a compare and contrast lessons of fairy tales.

Recount stories, including fables and folktales from diverse cultures, and determine their central message, lesson, or moral.

Compare and contrast two or more versions of the same story by different authors or from different cultures.

Students are able to find lots of differences between fairy tales. The characters, story events, perspectives, and setting are often the biggest differences. There will be similarities too. Often the problem/ solution and the main idea or central message will stay the same regardless of the version you read.

While reading fairy tales students can compare characters, story events, points of view, setting, problem and solution, main idea.

The following lesson plan is good for 4th grade students which can be used with Uzbek fairy tales.

Introductory part

Ask the following questions:

Do you enjoy reading fairy tales? Why or why not? What fairy tales have you heard from your parents?

What are fairy tales?

Can you tell me how do fairy tales begin?

What kind of characters are there in the Uzbek fairy tales?

Possible answers can be:

A fairy tale is a story written for children that has magic or imaginary beings and lands. Fairy tales are meant to be entertaining.

All fairy tales have certain elements that are the same. They begin with “Once upon a time...” and end with “And they lived happily ever after.”

There is always a good character and an evil character. One of the characters in the fairy tale is usually royalty, such as a prince, princess, king or queen. One of the characters is usually poor or from a poor working family.

Another element of a fairy tale is that something magical happens. There might be a spell cast, animals talking or fairies, trolls or elves.

Main part:

Ask the students to read two fairy tales. Tell them that while they are reading them, they should think about how they are the same and how they are different. Think about the different elements of a fairy tale and which elements they have. Then, you will fill in the table.

Table:

	Zumrad and Kimmat	Cinderella
Good character		
Bad character		
Royalty		
Magical elements		
Problem to be solved		
How it was solved		

Here are compare and contrast activities which can be used with one fairy tale. First ask the students to read the Uzbek fairy tale “The Brave Wind”.

THE BRAVE WIND

Beside a high mountain there lived a brave wind.

He was so strong, that he could rip big trees up in a minute, he could make waves in the river.

Once he became bored to death. He climbed to the top of a mountain and watched.

Suddenly he saw an ant, which was carrying an ear of wheat with difficulty. The Brave wind smiled and said laughing of him:

- Greenhorn, if I blow you will die!

The ant continued walking not paying attention to his words.

The Brave wind was angry because the ant continued on his way ignoring him and he blew again. Then the clever ant quickly hid under the bushes. The brave wind couldn't blow him, so he was ashamed of his behavior. There are was a cave in the mountain. When the Brave wind was returning home, he came down into the cave. He howled; hit all the sides trying to go out. But he could not find the way out and was worried of staying here for all his life. Suddenly his uncle the Storm came. He asked:

- What have you done?

- I wanted to blow the ant but I couldn't. When I was coming back I entered here.

Help me! - pleaded the wind

But his uncle the Storm said:

- You should promise me to serve for kindness ever after.

The wind promised. Then his uncle helped him. The wind was happy and ever after he served for kindness. Spanned the mills and blew as slight breeze in hot days.

These are the activities which can help to enhance logical and critical thinking of students.

Activity 1. The PMI strategy

A good brainstorming strategy you can use when making decisions is the PMI strategy. On a piece of paper, draw three columns and head them “plus”, “minus” and “interesting”. Write down the positive consequences (plus) and negative consequences (minus) of taking the decision, and also what would be “interesting” of carrying it out.

Strong wind decided to blow up the ant.

Strong wind spanned the mills and blew as light breeze in hot days.

Plus	Minus	Interesting
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Activity 2. The Strong wind decided to be kind. Think about the factors that influenced his decision. Write them in the table.

Factors

With a partner, think of other factors which make us behave well. Add them to the chart.

Activity 3. Reflecting. Complete the chart with information. When the two answers are the same, put a check in the third column. Then compare your answers with a partner.

	Strong wind	Uncle-Storm	The ant	You (now or in the future)	Same answer?
Hard working or lazy?					
Job?					
Age ?					
Male or female?					
Interests?					

Activity 4. Synthesizing and Reflecting. Think about your answers. What do you have in common with the Strong wind, ant, uncle? Discuss your answer in a small group.

Activity 5. Making Inferences. From the fairy tale, we can infer that the Strong wind is arrogant. Find and underline sentences in the fairy tale that show this.

Note: Inferring means understanding something that is not stated directly. When you make inferences about a person, for example, you guess information about that person by the things he or she says or does.

Activity 6. Synthesizing. Complete the Venn diagram to compare the Strong wind and you.

The development of logical thinking is inseparable from the formation of performance skills. The more versatile and perfect the abilities of schoolchildren are, the richer their imagination, the more realistic their design, the more complex logical problems they solve.

With thoughtful planning and refinement informed by research, teachers can realize significant pedagogical advantages.

To sum up, using the above activities can help to enhance primary school students` logical and critical thinking skills.

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